

Table 1. Example Data for Changes made to ToxRTool						
	Changes made to "Test Substance Identification"	Changes made to "Test System Characterization"	Changes made to "Study Design Description"	Changes made to "Study Results Documentation"	Changes made to "Plausibility of Study Design and Data"	Other changes not categorized based on the original ToxRTool 5 groups
<i>Burns and Davies</i>	1	1	1	1	1	5
<i>Card and Magnuson</i>	2	6	6	6	6	4
Frequency of 1s						
Frequency of 2s						
Frequency of 3s						
Frequency of 4s						
Frequency of 5s						
Frequency of 6s						
	1. modified all the question(s)	2. met original questions with modifications	3. added a question(s)	4. added a new "Criteria Group"	5. developed a new scoring system	6. none (not mentioned or addressed)

Table 1. Example Data for Changes made to ToxRTool. This table summarizes two example publications that made changes to ToxRTool. Each column represents the group where changes were made. To determine the frequency of changes made, the following numbers were assigned to potential changes: 1) modified all the question(s), 2) met original questions with modifications, 3), added a question(s), 4) added a new 'Criteria Group,' 5) Developed a new scoring system, or 6) none (not mentioned or addressed). Additional descriptions for each change is listed in Table 6. For example, Burns and Davies modified all the questions (1) in the group 'Test Substance,' 'Test System Characterization,' 'Study Design Description,' 'Study Results Documentation,' and 'Plausibility of Study Design and Data.' The authors authors also developed a new scoring system (5) as another modification not related to any of the prior five groups listed. But Card and Magnuson met original question with modifications (2) for the group 'Test Substance' and did nothing to groups ' Test System,' 'Study Design,' 'Study Results Documentation,' or 'Plausibility of Study Design and Data.'